

SZ-BB-II-01-01 Keeping a training record (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851112
ID	SZ-BB-II-01-01
Title	Keeping a training record
Educational area	#vocational-training
Persona	P: Jasper - Trainee https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091281 P: Claudia - instructor https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13644649
Short description	Jasper, an industrial mechanics apprentice, wants to optimise the management of his digital report book so that he can fill it in on time.
Result	In BIRD, Jasper finds user-friendly support for his report booklet.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "creating the workspace"• Part 2: "keeping a report booklet"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Jasper is registered at BIRD• Jasper is logged in to BIRD
Components	#workspace
Services / tools	#BIRD-Calendar #texteditor training_record (report booklet) BLoK: Digital online report booklet

Problem scenario

Introduction

Jasper Kempe is an apprentice industrial mechanic at Zeiss. To enable his trainer Claudia Mertens to track his progress, he has been given access to a digital training certificate tool. His local Chamber of Industry and Commerce recommends the app “[BLoK: Digital Online Report Book](#)”, which his trainer can access to digitally sign and comment on individual reports.

Problem definition

The web application provided to him for the report booklet is very limited in terms of formatting and editing entries. In addition, the app does not have a sufficient spell checker, which is why Jasper has decided to write his reports and notes in his own workspace and then transfer them to the app. Jasper struggles with his time management and often finds it difficult to find time every day to write his reports. He also needs a reminder for the web application so that he doesn't forget to fill out his report booklet.

Background and context

Everyone in vocational training must keep a training record. Jasper is not a native speaker, but he has to keep his report book in German. Sometimes he needs a little longer to find the right words or has to reread what he has written. The app is geared more toward native speakers.

Jasper is also not very good at time management. He finds it difficult to find (enough) time every day to fill out his report booklet. In the past, he has forgotten to fill out his report booklet in the web application a few times, causing him to miss deadlines.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Jasper is behind schedule and now really has to discipline himself to fill in the report booklet regularly, otherwise his trainer will talk to him about it and he will have to make up for the days he has missed at the end of his training. What's more, if he doesn't enter his work regularly, he forgets what he has done, which makes it even more difficult. He simply wants to do well because it is part of his training.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Jasper has already tried taking notes on his smartphone and then copying and pasting them into his report book. Of course, this is very cumbersome and does not save him any time. In addition, the notes lack spell check and grammar check, which are also important to him.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "creating the workspace"

Step 1: Jasper logs into BIRD, opens his personal workspace and creates a new project, labeled "Notes Report Book".

Step 2: Jasper loads various tools into the newly created project, including the text editor (with spell check), a calendar and the digital report tool "BLoK", where he can log in with BIRD SSO.

Step 3: The calendar imports the training weeks, and Jasper can now select which weeks the calendar should create in the document. The calendar then automatically names and numbers them.

Step 4: Jasper adds an entry to his calendar for each day of the week to remind him to work on his training record. He makes notes about the events, tasks and learning opportunities of each day.

Part 2: "keeping a report booklet"

Step 1: Jasper is reminded by his calendar to work on his report booklet via a notification. To do this, he opens his workspace in BIRD and then the "Report Booklet Notes" project, which he had previously created there. Jasper takes the necessary notes or rather continues writing his report.

Step 2: In the text editor, Jasper immediately checks the last part he has written for spelling mistakes so that he can transfer his report directly into the digital report book at the end of the week and does not have to spend unnecessary time for proofreading.

Step 3: At the end of each working week, Jasper opens the project in his workspace, reviews his notes and converts them into a coherent report.

Step 4: Jasper wants to export his notes from his Workspace to the digital report booklet. To do this, he opens the BLoK application alongside his notes and transfers the key points to the digital report booklet template.